

ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH DIRECTED TO THE GOALS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

Kalandarov Aybek Ruzimbayevich

(PhD)

Associate Professor of the Department of Romano-
Germanic Philology, Ma'mun University

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the status, relevance, and importance of scientific researches focused on sustainable development goals (SDGs). BRM is a set of important indicators set by the UN to achieve global sustainability by 2030. Within the framework of the article, directions of research aimed at balanced development of ecological, economic and social factors and their role in solving modern problems are studied. Also, the article examines the possibilities of increasing the efficiency of scientific research in achieving BRM and analyzes the possibilities of their results having a positive impact on society.

Key words: Sustainable development goals, scientific research, ecological balance, social issues, economic stability, innovative approaches.

Introduction.

At present, the issue of sustainable development is recognized as an urgent problem on a global scale. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted by the United Nations in 2015[1], are important directions set by 2030 in order to improve the quality of life of all people on earth, maintain ecological balance and ensure economic stability. This set of goals, consisting of 17 goals and 169 tasks[4], includes strategies for making positive changes in every area of humanity.

Scientific research plays an important role in the implementation of BRMs, because they offer modern and innovative approaches to the development of society and solving problems. However, the effectiveness of scientific research and its integration with BRMs depends on many factors. Therefore, this article aims to analyze the status, relevance and importance of scientific research aimed at the goals of sustainable development, as well as to study what results can be achieved through this research in the future. Scientific research related to BRMs can create new opportunities not only in academic circles, but also in practice, which helps to maintain a balance between society and the natural environment.

Scientific research focused on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) offers approaches aimed at balanced development of environmental, economic and social aspects. These studies are conducted in various fields and serve to

solve interrelated issues at the global and local levels within the framework of BRMs.

Ecological research: Research aimed at ensuring ecological sustainability is mainly focused on the use of natural resources, waste reduction and biodiversity conservation. For example, studying the use of renewable energy sources, research aimed at reducing the emission of harmful gases into the atmosphere has brought many successful results. Such studies are also important in assessing environmental impacts and developing conservation strategies.

Economic Research: Research conducted to ensure economic stability mainly studies innovative technologies, economic growth and employment[2]. Research on the development of small and medium-sized businesses, support for social entrepreneurship and reduction of economic inequality will further strengthen the economic aspects of BRMs. Research results often play a key role in the formation of economic policy.

Social Research: Research focused on social sustainability and justice, focusing on areas such as social inclusion, education and health. These studies are of fundamental importance in the development of programs aimed at supporting various layers of society, providing assistance to the needy and increasing their capabilities. The results of social research also play an important role in gender equality and the protection of the rights of disadvantaged groups.

The analysis of researches shows that scientific research within the framework of BRMs is carried out in interrelated and complementary directions. They are an effective tool for achieving sustainable development at the global and local levels. However, in order to increase the effectiveness of research, cooperation and integration are necessary, as well as the introduction of new innovative approaches and methodologies. Thus, scientific research will have not only theoretical, but also practical significance in the implementation of BRMs.

Discussion. Sustainable development is a set of actions to ensure ecological, social and economic balance in meeting the current and future needs of mankind. One of the key factors in achieving these goals is quality education. Education is an important tool aimed not only at imparting knowledge and skills, but also at stimulating personal development, increasing social responsibility, and implementing the principles of sustainable development.

1. *The relationship between education and sustainable development:*

Quality education introduces individuals to the goals of sustainable development and prepares them to actively contribute to society. Introducing concepts such as ecological balance, social equality and economic stability in the educational process encourages students to become responsible and conscious citizens in the future.

2. *Innovative educational approaches:* Innovative approaches play an important role in improving the quality of education. Interactive teaching methods, multi-disciplinary programs and practical experiences are effective methods of involving students in the educational process. Also, the use of digital technologies allows to modernize the educational process and connect it with global knowledge.

3. *Role of teachers:* The role of teachers in improving the quality of education is incomparable. Their professional qualification, ability to introduce innovations into the educational process and awareness of social responsibility are important factors in improving the quality of education. Continuous training of teachers and training in new approaches increases the effectiveness of the education system.

4. *Effective education policy:* Effective education policy is necessary to improve the quality of education in sustainable development. It is necessary to control and ensure quality at all stages of education, improve resources and infrastructure in educational institutions, provide quality education opportunities to all layers of society. In this process, it is important to strengthen cooperation between the state, private sector and non-governmental organizations[3].

5. *Social and environmental issues:* Quality education also contributes to sustainable development by imparting knowledge aimed at solving social and environmental issues. Studying issues such as environmental protection, social justice and cultural diversity in the educational process encourages students to actively participate in these areas.

Improving the quality of education in sustainable development is important not only for personal development, but also for the overall well-being of society. Knowledge and skills acquired through quality education serve as a powerful tool for future generations to achieve sustainable development goals. Therefore, improving the education system and increasing its quality remains a priority for every state and society. In this thesis, the importance, status and future prospects of scientific research focused on sustainable development goals

(SDGs) were analyzed. Research conducted within the framework of BRMs is aimed at the balanced development of environmental, economic and social aspects, and these studies are an important tool for achieving sustainable development at the global and local levels. However, it is necessary to solve a number of problems in order to increase the effectiveness of research and strengthen its integration with BRMs. Integration, multidisciplinary approaches and the use of innovative methodologies are important in strengthening the interdependence of research and obtaining practical results from them.

Conclusion. Also, effective cooperation between state and non-state organizations is necessary to pay attention to social issues and put research results into practice. In the path of sustainable development, scientific research should have not only theoretical, but also practical significance.

In order to achieve the goals of sustainable development in the future, it is necessary to strengthen the links between scientific research and practice, develop cooperation and introduce new approaches. Such approaches will undoubtedly have a positive effect on the development of society and the maintenance of ecological balance.

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